

Synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of trimethylsilicon- and tributyltin-tris(glycolato)niobates

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Abstract : Trimethylsilicon- and tributyltin- derivatives of the types $(\text{OGO})_2\text{Nb}(\text{OGOSiMe}_3)$ and $(\text{OGO})_2\text{Nb}(\text{OGOSnBu}_3)$ (where G = $\text{Me}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{CMe}_2$ (G^1) **1** (Si), $\text{CHMeCH}_2\text{CMe}_2$ (G^2) **2** (Si), Me_2CCMe_2 (G^3) **3** (Si), $\text{CH}_2\text{CMe}_2\text{CH}_2$ (G^4) **4** (Si), CHMeCHMe (G^5) **5** (Si), and G = G^1 **6** (Sn), G^2 **7** (Sn), G^3 **8** (Sn), G^4 **9** (Sn), G^5 **10** (Sn) have been prepared by the reactions of $\text{Nb}(\text{OGO})_2(\text{OGO})\text{H}$ with Me_3SiCl in the presence of Et_3N or with $n\text{-Bu}_3\text{SnOPr}^i$ in benzene. The new complexes **1-10** have been characterized by elemental analyses, cryoscopic molecular weight measurements, IR and NMR (^1H , ^{13}C , ^{29}Si , ^{119}Sn) spectroscopic studies.

Keywords : Glycolate complexes, niobium(v), trimethylsilicon, *n*-tributyltin, spectral properties.

Introduction

Our pioneering work on heterometallic alkoxide chemistry has earlier focused mainly on the use of alkoxometallate anions as effective and versatile chelating ligands^{1,2} to bind different metal atoms. Another convenient and useful preparative route developed by us during past 15 years rely on use of homometal complexes of di- and tri-hydroxy alcohols³ such as glycols⁴, diethanolamines⁵, and triethanolamine⁶ containing at least one remainder hydroxy group as a reactive site to bind different metal alkoxide/organometal(loid) fragment²⁻⁶. Deprotonated forms of polyhydroxy alcohols are suitable chelating/bridging units, which result in attractive molecular architectures through their versatile ligational modes³.

We report in this paper for the first time synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of niobium glycolate complexes containing a Me_3Si or $n\text{-Bu}_3\text{Sn}$ fragment.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

Equimolar reactions of niobium(v)tris(glycolato) com-

plexes, $\text{Nb}(\text{OGO})_2(\text{OGO})\text{H}$, in benzene with Me_3SiCl in the presence of Et_3N as proton acceptor (eq. (1)) or with $n\text{-Bu}_3\text{Sn}(\text{OPr}^i)$ (eq. (2)) afford complexes **1-5** and **6-10**, respectively :

All these colourless complexes (Table 1) are solids or viscous liquids, soluble in common organic solvents (e.g. benzene, toluene, dichloromethane, chloroform, and moderately in *n*-hexane), and depict monomeric nature

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Table 1. Preparative and analytical details of heteronuclear complexes **1-10**

Product (Empirical formula)	Yield (%) (g)	Et ₃ N.HCl/Pr ⁱ OH (g) Found (Calcd.)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				M. wt. Found (Calcd.)
			C	H	Si	Nb	
Nb(OG ¹ O) ₂ {OG ¹ OSiMe ₃ } 1 (C ₂₇ H ₅₇ O ₆ NbSi)	1.92 (68)	0.64 (0.65)	54.05 (54.16)	9.39 (9.60)	4.51 (4.69)	15.29 (15.52)	603 (598)
White solid							
Nb(OG ² O) ₂ {OG ² OSiMe ₃ } 2 (C ₂₁ H ₄₅ O ₆ NbSi)	2.30 (94)	0.62 (0.65)	49.17 (49.01)	8.83 (8.81)	5.31 (5.46)	17.90 (18.05)	523 (514)
Colourless viscous liquid							
Nb(OG ³ O) ₂ {OG ³ OSiMe ₃ } 3 (C ₂₁ H ₄₅ O ₆ NbSi)	1.67 (71)	0.60 (0.62)	49.01 (49.01)	8.59 (8.81)	5.21 (5.46)	17.84 (18.06)	510 (514)
White solid							
Nb(OG ⁴ O) ₂ {OG ⁴ OSiMe ₃ } 4 (C ₁₈ H ₃₉ O ₆ NbSi)	2.02 (68)	0.82 (0.86)	45.69 (45.75)	8.29 (8.32)	5.69 (5.94)	19.41 (19.66)	501 (472)
White solid							
Nb(OG ⁵ O) ₂ {OG ⁵ OSiMe ₃ } 5 (C ₁₅ H ₃₃ O ₆ NbSi)	1.80 (68)	0.55 (0.59)	42.08 (41.85)	7.71 (7.73)	6.24 (6.52)	21.32 (21.58)	452 (430)
Colourless viscous liquid							
Nb(OG ¹ O) ₂ {OG ¹ OSnBu ₃ } 6 (C ₃₆ H ₇₅ O ₆ NbSn)	2.26 (69)	0.23 (0.24)	52.84 (53.01)	9.17 (9.27)	25.30 ^a (25.95)		836 (815)
White solid							
Nb(OG ² O) ₂ {OG ² OSnBu ₃ } 7 (C ₃₀ H ₆₃ O ₆ NbSn)	2.96 (95)	0.24 (0.25)	49.21 (49.26)	8.73 (8.68)	28.32 ^a (28.93)		726 (731)
Colourless viscous liquid							
Nb(OG ³ O) ₂ {OG ³ OSnBu ₃ } 8 (C ₃₀ H ₆₃ O ₆ NbSn)	1.63 (71)	0.17 (0.18)	49.06 (49.26)	8.78 (8.68)	28.47 ^a (28.93)		757 (731)
White semi solid							
Nb(OG ⁴ O) ₂ {OG ⁴ OSnBu ₃ } 9 (C ₃₇ H ₅₇ O ₆ NbSn)	2.60 (66)	0.32 (0.34)	46.87 (47.04)	8.07 (8.33)	30.35 ^a (30.70)		698 (689)
White semi solid							
Nb(OG ⁵ O) ₂ {OG ⁵ OSnBu ₃ } 10 (C ₂₄ H ₅₁ O ₆ NbSn)	2.25 (95)	0.20 (0.21)	44.61 (44.53)	8.00 (7.94)	32.30 ^a (32.70)		630 (647)
Colourless viscous liquid							

^aDetermined as mixed metal oxides of tin and niobium.

cryoscopically in dilute benzene solution. However, the possibility of some sort of association in the solid state can not be ruled out.

Spectral studies :

IR spectra :

Infrared spectra (Table 2) of **1-10** exhibit absorptions due to niobium(V) attached glycolate groups^{4d} at $1350 \pm 30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\delta(\text{C-H})$ bending vibrations of Me₂C or MeHC groups, $1045 \pm 35 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\nu(\text{C-O})$ of Nb-O-C glyco-

late, $750 \pm 30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ $\rho(\text{CH}_2)$ rocking, and $572 \pm 18 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ $\nu(\text{Nb-O})^{4d}$ vibrations. The spectra of **1-5** exhibit additional bands for a Me₃SiO fragment⁷ at $1250 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{Si-CH}_3)$ symmetric deformation, $835 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $745 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to asymmetric and symmetric $\nu(\text{Si-C})$ vibrations. The band at $962 \pm 13 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assignable to $\nu(\text{Si-O})$ stretching vibration.

The complexes **6-10** show strong to medium intensity bands characteristic of Bu₃SnO⁸ group at $505 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu_s(\text{Sn-C})$ and at $603 \pm 8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ $\nu_{as}(\text{Sn-C})$ vibra-

tions. The bands due to $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$ vibrations appear at $542 \pm 8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

NMR characterization :

^1H NMR spectra (Table 2) of **1-10** show signals assignable to glycolate moieties almost in the same region as were earlier found for homoleptic tris(glycolato)-niobium(v) complexes, $\text{Nb}(\text{OGO})_2(\text{OGO})\text{H}$ ^{4d} and their derivatives, along with the signals due to Me_3Si ⁷ or *n*- Bu_3Sn ^{4c,8} group protons. For example, a singlet for Me_3Si in **1-5** appear at $\delta 0.11 \pm 0.0$, while *n*- Bu_3Sn protons in **6-10** show triplet for $\text{Me}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Sn}$ and a complex multiplet for methylene protons of *n*-butyl group, $\text{Me}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Sn}$ in the $\delta 0.91-0.92$ and $1.27-1.66$ region, respectively.

Compounds **1-10** exhibited peaks typical of appropriate glycolate groups. For example : **1, 3, 6,** and **8** revealed a singlet for Me_2CO protons at $\delta 1.25 \pm 0.01$, whereas in **2** and **7** signals for OCMe_2 are buried within the signals due to OCHMe group and appear as a complex multiplet in the region $\delta 4.22-4.61$. Compounds **4** and **9** exhibit a singlet and a broad peak at $\delta 0.96$ and 3.98 ± 0.10 for CMe_2 and CH_2O protons, respectively. Signals for glycolate group protons in all the new compounds **1-10** are shifted slightly downfield than those observed in the parent glycols.

^{13}C NMR spectral data (Table 3) for **1-5** revealed signals (δ , ppm) at : $1.01-1.12$ (SiMe_3), $16.90-24.53$

Table 2. IR and NMR spectral data for complexes **1-10**

Complex	IR (cm^{-1})	^1H NMR (δ , ppm)	$^{29}\text{Si}/^{119}\text{Sn}$
1	1360, 1320 $\delta(\text{CMe}_2)$; 1250 $\nu(\text{SiMe}_3)$; 1170, 1110, 1040 $\nu(\text{C-O})$; 965 $\nu(\text{Si-O})$; 830 $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{Si-C})$; 770 $\rho(\text{CH}_2)$; 750 $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{Si-C})$; 560 $\nu(\text{Nb-O})$	0.12 (9H, s, OSiMe_3); 1.24 (36H, s, OCMe_2); 1.69 (12H, s, CH_2)	12.17
2	1365, 1325 $\delta(\text{CMe}_2)$; 1265 $\nu(\text{SiMe}_3)$; 1190, 1140, 1080, 1040 $\nu(\text{C-O})$; 955 $\nu(\text{Si-O})$; 840 $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{Si-C})$; 772 $\rho(\text{CH}_2)$; 750 $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{Si-C})$; 550 $\nu(\text{Nb-O})$	0.11 (9H, s, OSiMe_3); 1.22–1.32 (27H, m, $\text{OCMe}_2 + \text{CCHMe}$); 1.70 (6H, s, CH_2); 4.61 (3H, m, OCHMe)	9.87
3	1375, 1330 $\delta(\text{CMe}_2)$; 1260 $\nu(\text{SiMe}_3)$; 1150, 1120, 1020 $\nu(\text{C-O})$; 975 $\nu(\text{Si-O})$; 840 $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{Si-C})$; 740 $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{Si-C})$; 570 $\nu(\text{Nb-O})$	0.11 (9H, s, OSiMe_3); 1.24 (36H, br, OCMe_2)	16.77
4	1380, 1340 $\delta(\text{CMe}_2)$; 1245 $\nu(\text{SiMe}_3)$; 1060, 1020 $\nu(\text{C-O})$; 945 $\nu(\text{Si-O})$; 835 $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{Si-C})$; 720 $\rho(\text{CH}_2)$; 590 $\nu(\text{Nb-O})$	0.12 (9H, s, OSiMe_3); 0.96 (18H, s, CMe_2); 4.08 (12H, br, CH_2O)	12.17
5	1370, 1340 $\delta(\text{CMe}_2)$; 1255 $\nu(\text{SiMe}_3)$; 1080, 1020 $\nu(\text{C-O})$; 950 $\nu(\text{Si-O})$; 840 $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{Si-C})$; 745 $\rho(\text{CH}_2)$; 555 $\nu(\text{Nb-O})$	0.10 (9H, s, OSiMe_3); 1.16–1.99 (18H, dd, J 5.62 Hz, OCHMe); 3.82 (6H, m, OCHMe)	12.49
6	1370, 1330 $\delta(\text{CMe}_2)$; 1150, 1045, 1015 $\nu(\text{C-O})$; 760 $\rho(\text{CH}_2)$; 600 $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{Sn-C})$; 585 $\nu(\text{Nb-O})$; 535 $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$; 510 $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{Sn-C})$	0.91 (9H, t, J 7.15 Hz, $(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Me}$); 1.26 (36H, s, OCMe_2); 1.28–1.60 (18H, m, $\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Me}$); 1.70 (12H, s, CH_2)	84.50
7	1366, 1320 $\delta(\text{CMe}_2)$; 1165, 1130, 1110, 1045, 1010 $\nu(\text{C-O})$; 780 $\rho(\text{CH}_2)$; 610 $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{Sn-C})$; 570 $\nu(\text{Nb-O})$; 550 $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$; 500 $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{Sn-C})$	0.92 (9H, t, J 7.15 Hz, $(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Me}$); 1.21–1.27 (27H, m, $\text{OCMe}_2 + \text{OCHMe}$); 1.31–1.59 (18H, m, $\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Me}$); 1.68 (6H, s, CH_2); 4.22 (3H, m, OCHMe)	90.13
8	1380, 1360 $\delta(\text{CMe}_2)$; 1150, 1070, 1040 $\nu(\text{C-O})$; 600 $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{Sn-C})$; 570 $\nu(\text{Nb-O})$; 535 $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$; 515 $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{Sn-C})$	0.91 (9H, t, J 7.15 Hz, $(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Me}$); 1.25 (36H, s, OCMe_2); 1.28–1.59 (18H, m, $\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Me}$)	
9	1360, 1320 $\delta(\text{CMe}_2)$; 1080, 1020, $\nu(\text{C-O})$; 595 $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{Sn-C})$; 560 $\nu(\text{Nb-O})$; 540 $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$; 515 $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{Sn-C})$	0.92 (9H, t, J 7.15 Hz, $(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Me}$); 0.96, 0.98 (18H, s, CMe_2); 1.27–1.60 (18H, m, $(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Me}$); 3.89 (12H, s, CH_2O)	109.85
10	1370, 1340 $\delta(\text{CHMe})$; 1060, 1015 $\nu(\text{C-O})$; 600 $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{Sn-C})$; 566 $\nu(\text{Nb-O})$; 545 $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$; 500 $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{Sn-C})$	0.91 (9H, t, J 7.24 Hz, $(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Me}$); 1.12–1.15 (18H, dd, J 5.60 Hz, OCHMe); 1.28–1.66 (18H, m, $(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{Me}$); 4.33 (6H, m, OCHMe)	82.40

Table 3. ^{13}C NMR (δ , ppm) spectral data for heteronuclear complexes **1-5**

Complexes	
1	1.02 (OSiMe ₃); 29.32, 29.82 (OCMe ₂); 38.20, 39.25 (CH ₂); 74.01, 76.62 (OCMe ₂)
2	1.01 (OSiMe ₃); 24.53, 30.66 (OCMe ₂ , OCHMe); 49.49, 51.04 (CH ₂); 65.23 (OCHMe); 71.52 (OCMe ₂)
3	1.10 (OSiMe ₃); 25.24, 25.54 (OCMe ₂); 76.63 (OCMe ₂)
4	1.12 (OSiMe ₃); 23.07, 23.55 (CMe ₂); 39.88, 40.35 (CMe ₂); 70.42, 73.70 (CH ₂ O)
5	1.03 (OSiMe ₃); 16.90, 17.31, 17.93, 19.27 (OCHMe); 70.82, 72.47, 74.43, 74.54 (OCMe)

(OCHMe), 23.07–30.66 (OCMe₂), 38.20–51.04 (CH₂), and 65.23–76.62 (OCHMe and/or OCMe₂).

The appearance of a sharp ^{29}Si NMR signal in the region δ 9.87–16.77 for compounds **1-5** (Table 2) is consistent with four-coordinate⁷ organosilicon compounds.

The observed sharp ^{119}Sn NMR signals (Table 2) in the δ 82.40–109.84 for **6-10** corroborate for four-coordinate⁹ environment around tin(IV) centre.

In view of the preceding discussion and available information in the literature^{4d,4e} on related systems it is more convincing that complexes **1-10** in solution are monomer with hexacoordinate niobium and tetra-coordinate both silicon and tin, $(\text{OGO})_2\text{Nb}(\text{OGOER}_3)$, where $G = G^1, G^2, G^3, G^4, G^5$; E, R = Si, Me; Sn, *n*-Bu). As it is possible for both the monomeric and dimeric species to have identical ^1H , ^{29}Si , ^{13}C , and ^{119}Sn chemical shifts, the dimeric structure of the type: $\text{Nb}_2(\{\eta^2\text{-(OGO)}\})_2(\{\mu\text{-}\eta^2\text{-(OGO)}\})_2(\{\eta^1\text{-(OGOER}_3)\})_2$ may be a possibility in the solid state. It is noteworthy that prior to this report there was not a single example in the literature for the type of compounds reported herein.

It was most disappointing that in spite of several repeated attempts none of these compounds **1-10** could produce crystallographically suitable crystals.

Experimental

All experiments were performed under strictly anhydrous conditions. Analytical grade (Merck, India) solvents were made anhydrous and purified by the literature methods¹⁰. Glycols: 2,5-dimethyl-2,5-hexanediol, HOG¹OH (Aldrich, 81.0 °C/0.2 mm); 2-methyl-2,4-

pentanediol, HOG²OH (Merck, 192.1 °C/746 mm); 2,3-dimethyl-2,3-butanediol, HOG³OH (Aldrich, 170.3 °C/746 mm); 2,2-dimethyl-1,3-propanediol, HOG⁴OH (Merck, 92.3 °C/0.4 mm); 2,3-butanediol, HOG⁵OH (Aldrich, 180.3 °C/746 mm) were dried by refluxing over Al(OPrⁱ)₃ in benzene and purified by distillation prior to use.

Niobium(v)tris(glycolato) complexes, Nb(OGO)₂(OGO_H) (where $G = G^1, G^2, G^3, G^4, G^5$) used as precursors for the synthesis of new complexes reported in this paper, were synthesized by the literature method^{4d}. Me₃SiCl (Fluka) was purified by distillation (57.0 °C/746 mm). Et₃N was dried by refluxing over KOH pellets, followed by distillation (88.8 °C/746 mm). *n*-Bu₃Sn(OPrⁱ) was prepared¹¹ by the reaction of *n*-Bu₃SnCl with NaOPrⁱ in benzene (*n*-Bu₃SnCl + NaOPrⁱ → *n*-Bu₃SnOPrⁱ + NaCl↓), followed by filtration and distillation (b.p. 125 °C/2.6 mm).

Silicon in compounds containing both Si and Nb was determined as SiO₂ by the literature method¹² and niobium¹³ was determined as Nb₂O₅ in the filtrate obtained after separation of precipitated SiO₂. The compounds containing tin and niobium were decomposed with a mixture of concentrated HNO₃ + HCl + H₂SO₄ and metal contents determined as mixed oxides. Isopropyl alcohol in the collected azeotrope was determined by oxidimetric method¹⁴.

Infrared spectra (400–4000 cm⁻¹) were recorded on SHIMADZU FT-IR-8400S spectrophotometer as Nujol mulls or neat in cases of mobile viscous liquids. NMR: ^1H (300.40 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS), ^{13}C (75.45 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS), ^{29}Si (59.60 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS), and ^{119}Sn (111.95 MHz, CDCl₃, SnMe₄) were recorded on JEOL AL 300 FT NMR spectrometer. Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O analyser was used to determine the carbon and hydrogen. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in benzene solution, using a Beckmann thermometer. Average of measurements on three solutions with concentrations in the 270 mg/20 ml – 350 mg/20 ml range in each case are reported in Table 1. The formula used for the calculation of molecular weight of the compounds is:

$$\text{M. wt.} = \frac{K_f \times W_e \times 1000}{\Delta t \times W_b}$$

where, K_f = freezing point depression constant (5.12 for benzene solution), W_c = weight of the compound taken, Δt = depression of freezing point (0 °C) and W_b = weight of benzene.

Synthesis of complexes 1-10 :

Due to the similarity in the synthetic procedure and also for the sake of brevity, synthetic details of only two representative complexes **1** and **6** are given below :

To a benzene (~40 ml) solution of Et_3N (0.48 g, 4.74 mmol) and Me_3SiCl (0.51 g, 4.69 mmol) was added $\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^1\text{O})_2(\text{OG}^1\text{OH})$ (2.48 g, 4.71 mmol) and the resulting turbid solution was allowed to stir at room temperature (30 °C) for 5 h. The precipitated $\text{Et}_3\text{N.HCl}$ (0.64 g) was removed by filtration. Removal of volatile components from the filtrate afforded white semi-solid compound **1** in 2.8 g (96%) yield. Recrystallization from a 1 : 5 mixture of dichloromethane and *n*-hexane at -20 °C yielded analytically pure compound **1** as white solid. Yield : 1.92 g (68%). Analytical details and some physical properties are given in Table 1.

Adopting the procedure that was used for **1**, compounds **2-5** were also prepared using appropriate reactants in desired stoichiometry :

$(\text{OG}^2\text{O})_2\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^2\text{OSiMe}_3) \quad \mathbf{2}$: [Prepared from $\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^2\text{O})_2(\text{OG}^2\text{OH})$ (2.11 g, 4.77 mmol), Me_3SiCl (0.52 g, 4.78 mmol) and Et_3N (0.48 g, 4.74 mmol)].

$(\text{OG}^3\text{O})_2\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^3\text{OSiMe}_3) \quad \mathbf{3}$: [Prepared from $\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^3\text{O})_2(\text{OG}^3\text{OH})$ (2.03 g, 4.59 mmol), Me_3SiCl (0.50 g, 4.60 mmol) and Et_3N (0.47 g, 4.64 mmol)].

$(\text{OG}^4\text{O})_2\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^4\text{OSiMe}_3) \quad \mathbf{4}$: [Prepared from $\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^4\text{O})_2(\text{OG}^4\text{OH})$ (2.52 g, 6.29 mmol), Me_3SiCl (0.68 g, 6.26 mmol) and Et_3N (0.64 g, 6.32 mmol)].

$(\text{OG}^5\text{O})_2\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^5\text{OSiMe}_3) \quad \mathbf{5}$: [Prepared from $\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^5\text{O})_2(\text{OG}^5\text{OH})$ (1.53 g, 4.27 mmol), Me_3SiCl (0.46 g, 4.23 mmol) and Et_3N (0.43 g, 4.25 mmol)].

Analytical details and some physical properties are

summarized in Table 1.

A colourless benzene (~50 ml) solution of $\text{Bu}_3\text{Sn(OPr}^i)$ (1.39 g, 3.98 mmol) and $\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^1\text{O})_2(\text{OG}^1\text{OH})$ (2.09 g, 3.97 mmol) was refluxed for 4 h under a fractionating column with continuous removal of liberated isopropyl alcohol (0.23 g), which was collected and determined periodically to monitor the progress of the reaction. When desired amount of the isopropyl alcohol was distilled out, refluxing was stopped and reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature. Volatiles from the solution were removed under reduced pressure to obtain white semi-solid compound **6** (3.2 g, ~99%). Recrystallization from *n*-hexane at -20 °C gave analytically pure complex **6** as a white solid in 2.26 g (69%) yield.

Analytical details are given in Table 1.

A procedure similar to **6** was used for the synthesis of complexes **7-10** using appropriate reactants in desired molar ratio as shown below.

$(\text{OG}^2\text{O})_2\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^2\text{OSnBu}_3) \quad \mathbf{7}$: [Prepared from $\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^2\text{O})_2(\text{OG}^2\text{OH})$ (1.88 g, 4.25 mmol), $\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOPr}^i$ (1.49 g, 4.27 mmol)].

$(\text{OG}^3\text{O})_2\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^3\text{OSnBu}_3) \quad \mathbf{8}$: [Prepared from $\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^3\text{O})_2(\text{OG}^3\text{OH})$ (1.39 g, 3.14 mmol), $\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOPr}^i$ (1.10 g, 3.15 mmol)].

$(\text{OG}^4\text{O})_2\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^4\text{OSnBu}_3) \quad \mathbf{9}$: [Prepared from $\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^4\text{O})_2(\text{OG}^4\text{OH})$ (2.28 g, 5.70 mmol), $\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOPr}^i$ (1.99 g, 5.70 mmol)].

$(\text{OG}^5\text{O})_2\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^5\text{OSnBu}_3) \quad \mathbf{10}$: [Prepared from $\text{Nb}(\text{OG}^5\text{O})_2(\text{OG}^5\text{OH})$ (1.30 g, 3.63 mmol), $\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOPr}^i$ (1.27 g, 3.64 mmol)].

Analytical details and some physical properties are summarized in Table 1.

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